

THE IMPORTANCE OF MODERN LESSON TYPES IN TEACHING CHEMISTRY AT MEDICAL HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

H. D. Abdullaeva

Assistant of Tashkent Medical Academy Urgench Branch

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15023372>

Abstract. This article explores the significance of modern lesson types in teaching chemistry at medical higher education institutions. It emphasizes the importance of a systematic approach to the educational process, incorporating various innovative pedagogical technologies. The article presents different lesson types, including debate lessons, lectures, seminars, experimental lessons, modular lessons, and problem-solving lessons, among others. It discusses the key knowledge and skills required by chemistry teachers, such as understanding educational objectives, using modern teaching methods, and developing students' problem-solving and research skills. Additionally, the article introduces the **ABCDE method** as an effective strategy for lesson planning, promoting efficiency and productivity. The topic "Digestion of Carbohydrates in the Body" is used as a case study to demonstrate how modern teaching methods can simplify complex concepts. The article concludes by highlighting the role of teachers in organizing students' cognitive activities in alignment with educational goals to enhance learning outcomes.

Keywords: Modern Lesson Types, Chemistry Education, Medical Higher Education, Pedagogical Technologies, ABCDE Method, Problem-Solving Skills, Interactive Teaching Methods, Carbohydrate Digestion, Lactose Intolerance, Educational Methodology, Teaching Efficiency.

The most effective lesson type is determined based on the objectives of the topic being taught and the content of education. A key condition for increasing the effectiveness of teaching chemistry in educational institutions is a systematic approach to the educational process. The types of lessons based on modern pedagogical technologies are presented in the following scheme:

Dars-lesson

Munozara darslari-debate lessons

Ma'ruza darslari-lecture

Seminar darslari-seminars

Modulli darslar-modules

Sinov darslari-experimental lessons

Didaktik oyin darslari-didactic game lessons

Erkin fikrlash darslari-free mindset lessons

Muammoli darslar-problem solving lessons

To organize such lessons effectively, a modern chemistry teacher must have knowledge of the following:

1. The objectives of chemistry education, including both the teaching goals and the developmental aims for students.

2. Educational programs, textbooks, and instructional materials used in academic institutions.

3. Theoretical foundations of chemistry teaching methodology, including teaching methods and assessment techniques, the use of laboratory equipment, safety protocols during experiments, the properties of chemical reagents, storage regulations, and technical teaching aids.

4. The development of students' problem-solving skills, as one of the key factors in fostering critical thinking. Therefore, the teacher must be proficient in solving chemical problems.

5. Scientific and creative research skills, which are essential for fostering independent research abilities among students. These skills are developed during pedagogical practice, leading to independent graduation projects that incorporate elements of scientific and methodological innovation.

6. Modern teaching methodologies, replacing traditional methods with interactive approaches, including innovative and information technologies.

For example, the ABSDE method is one of the most effective modern teaching techniques. Using this method, you can plan each of your lessons efficiently. It is simple yet highly beneficial, helping you become one of the most productive professionals in your field.

The more you think about planning and prioritizing before starting any task, the more time you will find for important activities, and the faster you will complete them. If the task you are working on is important and valuable to you, you won't postpone it—instead, you will feel motivated and fully immerse yourself in it.

The ABCDE method is a modern teaching technique that can be applied to every lesson. It is so simple and effective that, with its help, you can quickly become one of the most efficient and knowledgeable teachers in your field.

The letter A indicates that the task is very important. You must complete it.

Tasks are part of the essential work you need to complete.

S

Tasks at this level may not cause significant consequences if ignored, but completing them is still advisable.

D

Tasks that can be delegated to someone else fall into category D.

E

Tasks in this category can be skipped without any significant consequences.

Below, we will analyze the teaching of the topic "Digestion of Carbohydrates in the Body" using the ABCDE method.

A

Studying the digestion of carbohydrates in the body.

B

What foods are important for carbohydrate digestion?

S

The importance of salivary glands in carbohydrate digestion.

D

Lactase production in adults and symptoms of lactose intolerance.

E

Tests related to the topic.

As soon as we start eating, carbohydrate digestion begins. The salivary glands secrete hydrolytic enzymes that break α -glycosidic bonds, breaking down amylose and amylopectin into maltose, glucose, and sometimes dextrans composed of three to eight glucose units. The ingested food and partially digested starches then reach the stomach. In the acidic environment with a low pH, carbohydrate digestion stops.

Lactose Intolerance

The disaccharide lactose found in milk serves as an energy source and is broken down in the intestine with the help of the enzyme lactase. Infants and young children produce sufficient amounts of lactase, allowing them to digest lactose from milk efficiently. In rare cases, young children may experience lactase deficiency.

In adults, lactase production often decreases, leading to lactose intolerance, where the body cannot properly digest lactose. This condition affects approximately 25% of the world's population. Lactase deficiency is widespread across many regions globally.

(figure-1)

Og'iz-mouth

Laktoza-lactose

Glyukoza-glucose

Maltoza-maltose

Qon oqimi-blood pressure

Hujayralar-cells

Saxaroza-sucrose

Oshqozobn-stomach

Ingichka ichak- small intestine

Dekstrinlar-dextrins

Pankreatik amilaza- pancreatic amylase

Fruktoza- fructose.

Sulak amilazasi- salivary amylase

If lactose is not broken down into glucose and galactose, it cannot be absorbed through the intestines and remains in the gastrointestinal tract. In the intestines, lactose is fermented by bacteria, producing lactic acid, methane (CH₄), and carbon dioxide (CO₂) gases.

Symptoms of lactose intolerance appear within approximately 30 minutes to 1 hour after consuming milk or dairy products. These symptoms include nausea, abdominal cramps, and diarrhea. The severity of symptoms depends on the amount of lactose in the food and the amount of lactase the body produces.

Treatment of Lactose Intolerance

One of the primary ways to manage lactose intolerance is to avoid lactose-containing foods such as milk and dairy products, including cheese, butter, and ice cream. However, it is essential to consume alternative sources of calcium to maintain proper nutrition.

Some individuals who cannot tolerate milk products may still digest yogurt. This is because yogurt contains live bacterial cultures that produce lactase, which helps break down lactose. Therefore, yogurt can serve as a good calcium source for those with lactose intolerance.

It is also crucial for lactose-intolerant individuals to be aware of non-dairy foods that contain lactose. Certain bread products, cereals, breakfast drinks, and salad dressings may contain lactose. To avoid unwanted symptoms, always check food labels for ingredients like "milk" or "lactose."

Lactase enzyme supplements are available in various forms, such as tablets taken with meals, liquid drops added to milk, or chewable tablets. If lactase drops are added to milk and stored in the refrigerator for 24 hours, lactose levels can be reduced by 70–90%. Lactase tablets and chewable forms are typically consumed alongside meals that contain dairy products.

However, timing is essential—if there is a long delay between taking the enzyme and eating, stomach acid may break down too much lactase before it can effectively process lactose. If taken after a meal, the lactase enzyme helps lactose absorption in the small intestine (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Lactaid contains the enzyme lactase, which helps break down lactose.

Topic-Related Tests

1. What monosaccharides are produced when sucrose is hydrolyzed?
A) Glucose and Fructose

- B) Glucose and Lactose
C) Fructose and Starch
D) Mannose and Arabinose
2. What gas is produced during alcoholic fermentation of glucose?
A) CO₂
B) CO
C) SO₂
D) O₂
3. Identify the correct row of polysaccharides:
A) Cellulose, Starch, Inulin
B) Lactose, Glucose, Mannose
C) Starch, Fructose, Ribose
D) Fructose, Glucose, Ribose
4. Which carboxylic acid is formed as a result of fatty acid fermentation of glucose?
A) Butanoic acid
B) Propanoic acid
C) Pentanoic acid
D) Isobutyric acid
5. Identify the compound formed during lactic acid fermentation of glucose:
A) 2-hydroxypropanoic acid
B) Fructose
C) 2-aminopropanoic acid
D) Ribose
6. What percentage of carbohydrates is found in heart muscles?
A) 0.5%
B) 2%
C) 5-10%
D) 5-6%
7. Which substances are recommended as sucrose substitutes for diabetic patients?
A) Xylitol, Sorbitol
B) Sorbitol, Mannitol
C) Xylitol, Furfural
D) Mannitol, Xylitol
8. Accumulation of D-sorbitol in the vitreous body of the eye in diabetic patients can lead to which disease?
A) Cataracts
B) Mioma
C) Atherosclerosis
D) Hypertension
9. What percentage of lactose is found in human breast milk?
A) 6-8%
B) 4-5%
C) 10-15%

D) 25-30%

10. Which enzymes break down α -1,4 and α -1,6 glycosidic bonds in starch during digestion?

A) In saliva - amylase, in the intestine - maltase

B) In saliva - sucrase, in the intestine - hydrolase

C) In saliva - trypsin, in the intestine - mustin

D) In saliva - carboxylase, in the intestine - transferase

Conclusion: The effectiveness of the teaching process depends on the teacher's ability to organize students' cognitive activities in accordance with educational objectives and goals.

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